

Preregistration: Evaluation of the Bayley-4 Vision/Motor Accommodation Supplement (VMAS)

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1) Data collection Have any data been collected for this study already?

It's complicated. We have already collected some data but explain in Question 8 why readers may consider this a valid preregistration nevertheless.

2) Hypothesis What's the main question being asked or hypothesis being tested in this study?

The Bayley-4 (Bayley et al., 2024; Bayley & Aylward, 2019) Vision/Motor Accommodation Supplement (VMAS) contains accommodations to test materials and procedures that aim to ensure that the content and difficulty of the items remain unchanged, but a child with a motor and/or visual impairment can better demonstrate what he or she is capable of. The aim of the study is to evaluate if this is indeed the case. The research questions are:

1a. Does the VMAS improve the suitability of the Bayley-4 for children with cerebral palsy (cp)?

1b. Does this depend on the age of the child?

1c. Does this depend on the severity of cp?

2a. Does the VMAS improve the suitability of the Bayley-4 for children with visual impairment?

2b. Does this depend on the age of the child?

2c. Does this depend on the severity of the visual impairment?

3. Do the test results of children without impairment show measurement invariance between the Bayley-4 VMAS and Bayley-4 standard version?

Based on research into the previous version of the VMAS, the Bayley-III Special Needs Addition SNA (SNA; Visser et al., 2013), we hypothesize that questions 1a, 2a and 3 will be answered positively. Questions 1b, 1c, 2b, and 2c will be studied exploratively.

3) Dependent variable Describe the key dependent variable(s) specifying how they will be measured.

The main dependent variables are the test results of the children on the Bayley-4 standard and VMAS versions.

For question 1, the focus will be on the Cognition and Language scales. For questions 2 and 3, the Fine Motor subscale will additionally be taken into account, but does not have the priority, e.g., the Fine Motor subscale will be assessed when there is sufficient time.

The basal and ceiling rules and scoring guidelines of the standard Bayley-4 will be applied. All item scores are summed up to a raw score, which will be used in the analyses. The evaluation of measurement invariance will be based on the item scores, which can be 0 (no skill mastery), 1 (in development) or 2 (skill mastered).

Apart from the Bayley-4 test results, an additional dependent variable is the suitability of the two versions of the test for the child, as reported in an evaluation form by the person who administered the test.

4) Conditions How many and which conditions will participants be assigned to?

To evaluate the validity for children with impairment, a within-subject design will be used. More specifically, the children with cp or visual impairment (questions 1 and 2) will be assessed with both the standard Bayley-4 and the VMAS, so that a direct comparison of the scores will be possible. These test administrations will be done using a counterbalanced 2-in-1 design. This means that both versions will be assessed in one meeting. For half of the children, the standard version will be administered first; items that have a VMAS accommodation that are scored negatively (0 or 1) will be administered again using the VMAS version. For the other half, the VMAS version will be administered first; items where a VMAS accommodation was used on the initial administration and that are scored positively (1 or 2) will be administered again using the standard version.

The measurement invariance will be studied based on a between subjects design. More specifically, the children from the control group (3) will be assessed with the VMAS and the results will be compared to the existing standard Bayley-4-NL test results of the standardisation study.

5) Analyses Specify exactly which analyses you will conduct to examine the main question / hypothesis.

Analyses per research question (numbers refer to those under point 2):

Within the sample of children with cp:

1a. Regression analysis with the difference in raw score between the VMAS and standard versions as the dependent variable and the test order (dummy coded) as independent variable. The expectation is that the intercept will be larger than 0, indicating a higher raw score for the VMAS than for the standard version.

1b. Regression analysis as under 1a, with age in months added as an independent variable.

1c. Regression analysis as under 1a, with the Mini-MACS (Manual Ability Classification System; Eliasson et al., 2017) score as a measure of cp severity added as an independent variable.

Within the sample of children with visual impairment:

2a. Regression analysis with the difference in raw score between the VMAS and standard versions as the dependent variable and the test order (dummy coded) as independent variable. The expectation is that the intercept will be larger than 0, indicating a higher raw score for the VMAS than for the standard version.

2b. Regression analysis as under 2a, with age in months added as an independent variable.

2c. Regression analysis as under 2a, with the Visual Function Classification System (VFCS; Baranello et al., 2020; VFCS, n.d.) score as a measure of severity of visual impairment added as an independent variable.

In addition, we will summarize the results on the evaluation form to assess if the test administrator rated the VMAS to be more suitable than the standard version. More specifically, we will report descriptive statistics for the responses to the question "Could the child demonstrate what he or she is capable of?" (yes, but not due to the VMAS accommodations / yes, due to the VMAS accommodations / no) per group (cp and visual impairment) and also separately per mini-MACS / VFCS-level. For the second answer option, we will describe the responses to the question if this was due to the larger materials / adjusted colour of materials / modified test procedure, adjusted item instructions and / or other specified accommodations.

To answer RQ 3, we will perform multiple-group confirmatory factor analysis (MG-CFA; Millsap, 2012) to evaluate if measurement invariance is given between the VMAS version and the standard Bayley-4-NL. We will step-wise increase the restrictions to evaluate if configural, strong, and strict invariance holds. This will be done on the item level for each scale (Cognition, Receptive Language, Expressive Language, and Fine Motor skills) separately. The hypothesis will be confirmed if strong MI holds, as this implies that the factor means are comparable across groups.

For judging fit of the models assessing configural invariance, we will use the root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) $\leq .06$ and comparative fit index (CFI) $\geq .95$ (Hu & Bentler, 1999). For judging the change in fit for the models with strong and strict measurement invariance, we will use $\Delta CFI \leq$

-.01 (Cheung & Rensvold, 2002). *If multiple models display good fit based on these criteria, we will choose the model with the lowest Akaike information criterion (AIC).*

6) Outliers and Exclusions Describe exactly how outliers will be defined and handled, and your precise rule(s) for excluding observations.

In each of the samples (cp, visual impairment, and control group), we will exclude cases per subscale if there are more than three not-scored items or when the test administrator indicates that the results are unreliable. In addition, we will inspect extreme outliers, again separately for each sample and subscale. If we find a reason to suspect the outliers to be implausible, we will exclude them. If not, we will run the analyses with and without these outliers (Simmons et al., 2011).

In the MGCFAs, we will exclude data from items when they are completed by fewer than 10 children (Vittinghoff & McCulloch, 2007) or have no variance.

7) Sample Size How many observations will be collected or what will determine sample size? No need to justify decision, but be precise about exactly how the number will be determined. *For the samples for RQ 1 and 2, comparisons of the test-results will be done using manifest methods. Because we want to study differences between children from different ages and different degrees of impairment, and would like to differentiate between at least four levels, a sample size of 120 per group is needed.*

For the control group (RQ 3), the results will be analysed using MGCFAs, which is based on structural equation modelling (SEM). An absolute minimum for the sample size in SEM is 100 to 150; “For multi-group modelling, the rule of thumb is 100 cases/observations per group” (Wang & Wang, 2012, p. 392). We need relatively high power, because we expect the 0-hypothesis to be supported (i.e., we expect equivalence). Therefore, we aim at an effective sample size of 120 instead of 100.

An effective sample size means that we have data based on actually administered items, and not scores that were filled in because they were below the basal or above the ceiling. For calculating the effective sample size, we looked at the Cognition scale, because this includes the highest number of items. Counting with an average of 25 items that are administered per child (based on experiences in the standardisation study) and 10% missing data, we need a total N of approximately 400 to make sure we will have 133 gross = 120 net observations per item.

8) Other Anything else you would like to pre-register?

Data collection has started in July 2025 and will run until June 2026. The data collected so far has not yet been prepared or analysed.

Some content of this preregistration has been copied or adapted from the approved ethics application text (Ethics Commission Faculty of Social Sciences, Radboud University, reference number ECSW-2023-133R1).

If the group of children with visual impairment up to 24 months of age is sufficiently large, we might additionally run the analysis for RQ 2c on this subgroup and with the result of the Preverbal Visual Assessment (PreViAs; García-Ormaechea et al., 2014; Pueyo et al., 2014), instead of the VFCS, as a covariate, because this is a more differentiated measure, but only valid up to 24 months of age.

If sufficient information will be available on the type of cp, we might additionally run the analysis for RQ 1c with the type of cp (unilateral vs. bilateral) as a covariate, to evaluate if the added value of the VMAS depends on the type of cp (in addition to the severity).

9) Name Give a title for this AsPredicted pre-registration

Name:

Evaluation of the Bayley-4 Vision/Motor Accommodation Supplement (VMAS) for children with cerebral palsy and/or visual impairment: an international study

Study description:

The Bayley-4 is an instrument for developmental assessment of children up to 3.5 years of age. For the previous version (Bayley-3), a Special Needs Addition (SNA) has been developed and evaluated, consisting of Low Motor/Vision (LM/LVi), Low Verbal, and dynamic versions. Most interest from clinicians and researchers has been expressed for the Low Motor/Vision version.

Therefore, the aim of the current international project is to more specifically evaluate this LM/LVi, which has been adapted to the Bayley-4 and renamed "VMAS", for children with cerebral palsy or with a visual impairment. In addition, based on test administrations with children without impairment, the measurement invariance of the VMAS will be studied more extensively than has been done for the previous edition.

The Bayley-III SNA has been studied and published in the Netherlands only. The current project is an international one, with data collection for the special needs groups in the Netherlands, Germany, Australia, and the USA. The publisher, Pearson, is funding the research project and the research plan has been developed in collaboration with them. Depending on the study results, Pearson plans to publish the new Bayley-4 VMAS in Dutch, German, English, Swedish, Norwegian, Danish, Spanish, and French.

10) Type of study

Observational/archival study

11) Data source

n/a

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